

ISic3854

I.Sicily inscription 3854

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

volcanic (pietra di Serra)

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

exact findspot unknown

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, Museo Archeologico

Regionale Eoliano "Luigi Bernabò Brea", inventory 12330

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI334280

1. Ζωσίμας.

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

PHI 334280

Bibliography

Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M., Campagna, L. 2003. Meligunìs Lipára. XII. Le iscrizioni lapidarie greche e latine delle isole eolie. Palermo. At 178

Libertini, G 1921. Le isole eolie nell'antichità greca e romana. Ricerche storiche ed archeologiche. Florence. At 223 no.34

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